

A Study on Breast Cancer Awareness among Females in the Reproductive Age Group Residing in the Field Practice Area of Chengalpattu Medical College

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Abstract

Introduction: Breast cancer is the first most common cancer in women in India. Early diagnosis and treatment of breast cancer have significantly higher survival rates and significantly reduced the probability of the cancer being fatal. The main objective is to study the Knowledge about breast cancer, assess the Practice of Breast Self-examination (BSE), and compare the existing knowledge and practice among women in urban and rural areas. According to GLOBOCAN, Breast Cancer is fairly common in the younger age group (25 to 49 years), accounting for almost 37.7% of all cases. Since very few community-based studies including both rural and urban areas were done in south India, I have undertaken this study in females of the reproductive age group.

Methodology: A community-based cross-sectional study was conducted among 110 Females of the reproductive age group residing in the field practice area of Chengalpattu Medical College, 55 from rural and 55 from urban areas. Multi-stage random sampling was done. Institutional Ethical committee approval was obtained. After getting informed consent, data collection was done using a structured questionnaire. The data was entered in Microsoft Excel and analyzed using SPSS version 25.

Results: The mean age of the study participants was 32.91±8.21 years. All the study participants had heard about breast cancer. 44.5% of the study participants had adequate knowledge about breast cancer. Among those who had adequate knowledge about breast cancer majority 52.7% (n=29) were from urban areas and 36.4% (n=20) were from rural areas. 13.6% had performed BSE, and 10.9% Practiced BSE once a month. Study participants with educational status higher secondary and above had adequate knowledge of breast cancer than those with lesser education (p-value 0.010*). There was a statistically significant association between knowledge about breast cancer and the practice of BSE (p-value 0.000*). Study participants in urban areas practiced BSE more than in rural areas (p-value 0.024).

Conclusion: The study concludes that less than half (44.5%) of the study participants had adequate knowledge about breast cancer but only 13.6% had practiced BSE, and 10.9% of the study participants practiced BSE once a month. Study participants in urban areas practiced BSE more than those in rural areas. Intensive Behaviour Change Communication is to be given to the general public regarding breast cancer awareness and the importance of BSE. Improving access to clinical breast examination and Imaging techniques for screening breast cancer in all health facilities enables the detection of breast cancer at the earlier stage.

Keywords: Breast Cancer, Breast Self-examination, Knowledge, Practice.

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Introduction

Breast cancer is the most commonly diagnosed cancer type, accounting for 1 in 8 cancer diagnoses worldwide[1]. In 2022, there were 2.3 million

women diagnosed with breast cancer and 670,000 deaths globally. From being fourth in the list of most common cancers in India during the 1990s, it has

now become the first most common cancer in India [2]. Breast cancer occurs in women in every country of the world at any age after puberty but with increasing rates in later life [3]. Current trends point out that a higher proportion of breast cancer is occurring at a younger age in Indian women, as compared to the West [2]. GLOBOCAN predicted that cancer cases in India would increase to 2.08 million, accounting for a rise of 57.5 percent in 2040 from 2020 [4]. According to the World Cancer Report 2020, the most efficient intervention for Breast cancer control is early detection and rapid treatment [2]. A recent SURVCAN-3 study (Cancer Survival in Countries in Transition) published in 2023 found that the 3-year median survival for breast cancer across countries was 84%, whereas, in India, it was 68% worldwide [5]. The primary tools used for early disease detection are Breast Self-Examination (BSE), Clinical Breast Examination (CBE), and Mammography. Proper and regular implementation of these is regarded as the main preventive strategy for breast cancer. BSE helps in early detection of breast cancer and can detect 40% of the breast lesions. Early detection of breast cancer has a positive correlation with decreased morbidity and mortality, along with substantial healthcare savings [6].

BSE is considered to be a simple, inexpensive, non-invasive, and non-hazardous intervention, which is not only an acceptable, cost-effective, and appropriate method of early detection of cancer but also encourages women to take an active responsibility in preventive health. BSE is the most important individual preventive health strategy to be practiced by women regularly. However, correct and thorough BSE has to be ensured, and prompt medical help should be available when needed [7].

BSE benefits women in two ways: women become familiar with both the appearance and the feel of their breasts and detect any changes in their breasts as early as possible [8]. Breast cancer is one of the leading causes of death as it is detected in the late stages in India. Lack of awareness regarding the risk factors and breast self-examination acts as the causative factor for late diagnosis [9].

Early diagnosis and treatment of breast cancer have significantly reduced the probability of the cancer being fatal. According to GLOBOCAN, Breast Cancer is fairly common in the younger age group (25 to 49 years), accounting for almost 37.7% of all

cases for the year 2018 [10], and since very few community-based studies were done including both rural and urban areas in South India, I undertook this study in females of the reproductive age group.

Objectives

- To study the Knowledge about breast cancer among females in the reproductive age group residing in the field practice area of Chengalpattu Medical College.
- To assess the Practice of Breast Self-examination (BSE) among the study participants.
- To compare the knowledge and practice among the study participants in urban and rural areas.

Methodology

Study Settings, Design and Period

A community-based cross-sectional study was conducted among 110 Females of the reproductive age group residing in the field practice area of Chengalpattu Medical College, 55 from rural and 55 from urban areas. The study period was from October 2023 to December 2023.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Females in the reproductive age group residing in the field practice area of Chengalpattu Medical College who were willing to participate in the study were included in the study. Pregnant and lactating females were excluded from the study.

Sample Size Calculation and Sampling Method

As per a Study conducted by Prusty et al [11], in Mumbai, India from 2018 to 2019, 49% of the women were aware of breast cancer. Considering this 49% as Prevalence p with a relative precision (d) as 20% using the formula, $n = z^2 \frac{p \times q}{d^2}$, the sample size comes to 100, assuming 10% non-responsiveness, the minimal arrived sample size is 110.

Figure 1 shows that in the field practice areas of Chengalpattu Medical College, there were 1 urban and 3 rural blocks, Multistage Random sampling was done. 55 females from urban areas and 55 females from rural areas were selected for the study. To select blocks, villages, wards, and streets, simple random sampling was applied and systematic random sampling was applied to select houses.

Figure 1: Sampling method – Multistage Sampling

Data Collection Procedure

The study protocol was presented to the Institutional Ethics Committee of Chengalpattu Medical College. Institutional Ethical committee approval was obtained. The details of the study were explained to the study participants in their local language, and only after their understanding and willingness to participate in the study, informed written consent was obtained. Then the study participants were interviewed using the structured questionnaire by face-to-face interview. The interview was conducted privately and confidentiality was ensured to the study participants.

Data Collection Tool

The interviewer-administered structured questionnaire had questions regarding Breast cancer awareness, Breast cancer risk factors, signs and symptoms, screening tests, and the Practice of Breast self-examination.

The Questionnaire was originally prepared in English then translated into the local Tamil language, and re-translated again to ensure the appropriateness.

Finally, a structured validated questionnaire in the regional language (Tamil) was used for data collection which has the following sections.

Section 1: Socio-demographic profile & Family history

Section 2: Knowledge about breast cancer

Questions under this section were about risk factors for developing breast cancer such as Family history of breast cancer, obesity, harmful use of alcohol, reproductive history (such as age at menstrual periods began, age at menopause, and age at first pregnancy), and postmenopausal hormone therapy, Signs and Symptoms of breast cancer, the screening

test for breast cancer and their Knowledge about Breast Self-examination.

For the questions in knowledge, for each correct response score of 1 is given, for incorrect answers and not-answered questions score of 0 is given, out of a total score of 32, the Median is taken as the cutoff score. With a score of equal to and greater than 16, the participant is said to have adequate knowledge, Score of less than the Median Score the participant is said to have inadequate knowledge.

Section 3: Practice of Breast Self-examination

Questions under this section were about the practice of Breast Self-examination.

Data Analysis

The data was entered in MS Excel and analyzed using SPSS Version 25. Appropriate descriptive and inferential statistics like the Chi-square test, and Fisher's Exact Test were done and a p-value of <0.05 was taken as statistically significant.

Operational Definition

Reproductive Age Group Females

As per the World Health Organisation, women in the age group of 15 to 49 years of age are reproductive age group females [12].

Results

Table 1 shows a total of 110 females in the reproductive age group participated in this study, of which 55 were from rural areas and 55 were from urban areas. The majority of the study participants were ≥ 30 years of age. The mean age of the study participants was 32.89 ± 8.186 years, 74.5% of the study participants were Housewives, 93.6% were married, and 63.6% had two or more children. The majority of the study participants, 37.3% belong to the Middle Class as per Modified BG Prasad's Classification [13]

Table: 1 Sociodemographic Details

Variables		Frequency (n=110)	Percent
Age Group	<30 years	42	38.2%
	≥30years	68	61.8%
Educational	Illiterate	6	5.5%
	Literacy up to High School	45	40.9%
	Higher Secondary and above	59	53.6%
Occupation	Unemployed	82	74.5%
	Employed	28	25.5%
Marital Status	Single	7	6.4%
	Married	103	93.6%
Number of Children	≥2 Child	70	63.6%
	<2 Child	40	36.4%
Socio Economic Status (Modified BG prasad)	Upper Class	24	21.8%
	Upper Middle Class	29	26.4%
	Middle class	41	37.3%
	Lower Middle Class	16	14.5%

Family History of Breast Cancer

In this study, 3.6% of the study participants had a family history of breast cancer in their family.

In this study, all the study participants heard about breast cancer, and the majority of them 35.5% knew by television.

In this study, 69.1% of the study participants were aware that breast can occur in both younger and older age groups

Figure 2: Breast cancer risk factors knowledge(n=110)

Figure 2 In this study 46.4% of study participants knew the family history of breast cancer as a risk factor for breast cancer, and 34.5% of study participants knew Prolonged oral contraceptive intake as a risk factor for breast cancer. 28.2% of the study participants knew high alcohol intake as a risk factor for breast cancer.

Figure 3: Breast Cancer Signs and Symptoms Knowledge

Figure 3 shows that in this study, 89.1% of the study participants knew breast cancer presents with a lump in the breast, 82.7% were aware breast cancer may or may not present with pain, 60.90% knew any change in the size or shape of breasts might be the risk factor for breast cancer, 44.5% knew breast cancer might present with nipple discharge and 39.10% knew breast cancer might present with a lump in the armpit, 32.7% knew breast cancer might present with nipple indrawing, 26.4% were aware of skin changes. In this study, 44.5% (n=49) of the study participants had adequate knowledge about breast cancer. Among the study participants who had adequate knowledge majority 52.7% (n=29) were from urban areas and 36.4% (n=20) were from rural

areas but there was no statistically significant association between residence and knowledge about breast cancer. 64.5% were aware of BSE, 20.9% knew how to do BSE, 13.6% had practiced BSE, and 10.9% of study participants practiced BSE once a month. In this study, 60% of the study participants were aware of CBE. CBE is done free of cost for all women ≥ 30 years of age in government hospitals in Tamil Nadu under the Makkalai Thedi Maruthuvam scheme. 10% of the study participants were aware breast cancer can occur even in males. 72.7% knew breastfeeding protects against breast cancer. 87.3% knew early diagnosis and treatment improve the survival of patients with breast cancer.

Figure 4: Screening Procedure Awareness

Figure 4: In this study, 72.7% of the study participants were aware of CBE, 64.5% were aware of BSE, 36.4% were aware of breast ultrasonogram and 20.9% were aware of the mammogram.

Table 2: Factors Influencing Breast Cancer Knowledge

Variables		Knowledge		Test and value	P value
		Adequate knowledge	Inadequate Knowledge		
Age Group	<30 years (n=42)	23(54.8%)	19(45.2%)	Chi-Square test 2.871	0.090
	≥30 years (n=68)	26(38.2%)	42(61.8%)		
Residence	Urban (n=55)	29(52.7%)	26(47.3%)	Chi-Square test 2.981	0.084
	Rural (n=55)	20(36.4%)	35(63.6%)		
Education	Illiterate (n=6)	1(16.7%)	5(83.3%)	Chi-Square test 9.263	0.010*
	Up to HighSchool (n=45)	14(31.1%)	31(68.9%)		
	HigherSecondary and above (n=59)	34(57.6%)	25(42.4%)		
Occupation	Not Working (n=82)	33(40.2%)	49(59.8%)	Chi-Square test 2.413	0.120
	Working(n=28)	16(57.1%)	12(42.9%)		
Marital Status	Single(n=7)	6(85.7%)	1(14.3%)	Fisher Exact Test 5.129	0.043*
	Married(n=103)	43(41.7%)	60(58.3%)		
Number of Children	≥2 child(n=70)	26(37.1%)	44(62.9%)	Chi-Square test 4.270	0.039*
	<2 child(n=40)	23(57.5%)	17(42.5%)		
Socio Economic Status (Modified BG prasad)	Upper(n=24)	14(58.3%)	10(41.7%)	Chi-Square test 3.151	0.369
	Upper Middle(n=29)	13(44.8%)	16(55.2%)		
	Middle(n=41)	17(41.5%)	24(58.5%)		
	Lower Middle(n=16)	5(31.3%)	11(68.7%)		
Undergone Screening	Undergone Screening(n=15)	8(53.3%)	7(46.7%)	Chi-Square test 0.543	0.461
	Not Undergone(n=95)	41(43.2%)	54(56.8%)		

Table 2, shows that study participants with an educational status higher secondary and above had adequate knowledge of Breast Cancer than those with lesser education and the association was found to be statistically significant (p-value 0.010*).

Though the majority of the study participants with adequate knowledge were from urban areas, there was no statistically significant association found between residence and breast cancer knowledge.

Study participants who were married had adequate knowledge of Breast Cancer than those who were single and the association was statistically significant (p-value 0.043*).

Study participants with two or more than two children had adequate knowledge of Breast Cancer than those with single or no children and the association was statistically significant (p-value 0.039*).

Table 3: Factors Influencing Breast Self-Examination

Variables		Practice of BSE		Test and value	P value
		Yes	NO		
Age group	<30 years(n=42)	10(23.8%)	32(76.2%)	Chi-Square test 5.971	0.015*
	≥30 years(n=68)	5(7.4%)	63(92.6%)		
Residence	Urban(n=55)	12(21.8%)	43(78.2%)	Fisher's Exact test 6.253	0.024*
	Rural(n=55)	3(5.5%)	52(94.5%)		
Education	Illiterate(n=6)	1(16.7%)	5(83.3%)	Chi-Square test 3.159	0.206
	Upto HighSchool (n=45)	3(6.7%)	42(93.3%)		
	Higher Secondary and above (n=59)	11(18.6%)	48(81.4%)		

Occupation	Not Working (n=82)	10(12.2%)	72(87.8%)	Chi-Square test 0.568	0.451
	Working (n=28)	5(17.9%)	23(82.1%)		
Marital Status	Single (n=7)	3(42.9%)	4(57.1%)	Fisher's Exact test 5.420	0.052
	Married (n=103)	12(11.7%)	91(88.3%)		
Number of Children	≥2 child (n=70)	6(8.6%)	64(91.4%)	Chi-Square test 4.193	0.041*
	<2 child (n=40)	9(22.5%)	31(77.5%)		
Socio-Economic Status (Modified BG prasad)	Upper (n=24)	6(25%)	18(75%)	Chi-Square test 4.526	0.210
	Upper Middle (n=29)	2(6.9%)	27(93.1%)		
	Middle (41)	6(14.6%)	35(85.4%)		
	Lower Middle (n=16)	1(6.2%)	15(93.8%)		
Undergone Screening for Breast Cancer	Undergone Screening (n=15)	5(33.3%)	10(66.7%)	Chi-Square test 5.722	0.017*
	Not Undergone (n=95)	10(10.5%)	85(89.5%)		

Table 3 shows that study participants aged ≥ 30 years practiced BSE more compared to < 30 years and the association was found to be statistically significant (p-value 0.015*). Study participants in urban areas practiced BSE more than those in rural areas and the association was statistically significant (p-value 0.024*).

Study participants with two or more than two children had practiced BSE than those with single or no children and the association was found to be statistically significant (p-value 0.041*). There was a statistically significant association found between those who had undergone screening tests for breast cancer and practiced BSE (p-value 0.017*).

Table 4: Association between Breast Cancer Knowledge and Breast Self-examination Practice

Variable Breast Cancer Knowledge	Breast Self-examination Practice		Statistical Test Value Df	P Value
	Yes	No		
Adequate Knowledge (n=49)	15(30.6%)	34(69.4%)	Fisher's Exact test 21.622 Df=1	0.000*
Inadequate Knowledge (n=61)	0(0.0%)	61(100%)		

From Table 4, it is clear that study participants with adequate knowledge of breast cancer practiced Breast Self-examination more than those with inadequate knowledge. The association was found to be statistically significant (p-value 0.000*).

Discussion

The current study was a Community-Based Cross-Sectional Study conducted to study the Knowledge about Breast Cancer and to assess the Practice of Breast self-examination among females in the reproductive age group residing in the field practice area of Chengalpattu Medical College.

This study is important, as Breast cancer is the most common cancer in women in India. Lack of awareness regarding the risk factors, signs, symptoms of breast cancer and lack of knowledge about breast self-examination may be the reason for late diagnosis. Early diagnosis and treatment of breast cancer have significantly improved survival and reduced the probability of the cancer being

fatal. As per the GLOBOCAN database for the year 2018, Breast Cancer is fairly common in the younger age group (25 to 49 years). This study included 110 females in the reproductive age group. The mean age of the study participants was 32.91 ± 8.21 years and the majority of the study participants were ≥ 30 years of age.

This study was a Community-based study similar to the study conducted by Okyere et al[14]

In this study, females in the reproductive age group, 15 to 49 years were included similar to the study conducted by Okyere et al[14] (15 to 49 years) because breast cancer can occur even in younger age groups. Whereas in the study conducted by Prusty et al[11] (18 to 55yrs) Sachdeva et al[6] (> 30 years), Divya et al[9] (> 20 years), Dey et al [15] (18 to 70 years) were included.

In this study, participants included both from rural and urban areas, similar to the study conducted by Okyere et al[14] and Ramakant et al[16], in contrast

to the study conducted by Yerpude et al [7] and Divya et al [9] included participants only from rural areas.

In this study, participants with an educational status higher secondary and above had adequate knowledge of Breast Cancer than those with lesser education similar to the study conducted by Okyere et al [14] and Sharma et al [17] this might be because as educational status increases knowledge also increases

In this study, participants who were married had adequate knowledge of Breast Cancer than those who were single similar to the study conducted by Sharma et al [17].

In this study, participants aged ≥ 30 years practiced BSE, in contrast to the study conducted by Dadzi and Adam et al [18] this might be because in Tamil Nadu under the Makkalai Thedi Maruthuvam Scheme, screening for breast cancer is done for women ≥ 30 years of age and taught how to do Breast self-examination.

In this study, participants with ≥ 2 children practiced BSE similar to the study conducted by Okyere et al [14] participants with ≥ 3 children practiced BSE this might be due to increased exposure to hospitals for antenatal checkups, safe confinement, and child care.

In this study, 55.5% of the study participants had inadequate knowledge about breast cancer which was slightly similar to the study conducted by Jadhav et al [19] 58% of the study participants had inadequate knowledge about breast cancer this might be due to a lack of awareness about breast cancer.

In this study, participants with adequate knowledge of breast cancer practiced BSE more than those with inadequate knowledge similar to the study conducted by Sarker et al [20] this could be because "What the brain knows the eyes see".

In this study, participants in urban areas practiced BSE more than those in rural areas, similar to the study conducted by Okyere et al [14], this might be because of easy accessibility to health care services. In this study, 13.6% had practiced BSE which was closer to the results of the study conducted by Baburajan et al [21] 9.6% performed BSE, Hemalatha Kumarasamy et al [22] 18% of the participants practiced BSE, Yerpude et al [7] 22.6% had ever checked their breasts, Veena KS et al [23] 20% of the women practice BSE monthly once, Parle J et al [24] 25.8% of the respondents reported to perform BSE monthly and by Sarker et al [20] 21.3% had ever practiced BSE.

Conclusion

This study concludes that 44.5% of the study participants had adequate knowledge about breast cancer. However, only 13.6% had practiced Breast Self-examination, of which 10.9% practiced BSE monthly, which was not satisfactory. Study participants aged ≥ 30 years practiced BSE more compared to < 30 years. Study participants with educational status higher secondary above had adequate knowledge of Breast Cancer than those with lesser education. Study participants in urban areas practiced BSE more than those in rural areas. Study participants with two or more two children had adequate knowledge about breast cancer and practiced BSE. Study participants with adequate knowledge of breast cancer practiced BSE more than those with inadequate knowledge. Adequate knowledge about breast cancer and correct practice of BSE monthly aids in early detection and prompt treatment of breast cancer.

Limitation

This study only includes females of the reproductive age group, 15 to 49 years age and does not cover females of ages beyond it, as there is a twofold increase in the incidence of Breast cancer beyond the age of 50, also this study was done with a limited number of samples.

Recommendations

- Intensive Behaviour Change Communication is to be given to the general public regarding breast cancer and the importance of BSE.
- To strengthen the IEC-related activities regarding breast cancer and the importance of BSE in Outpatient Care in all healthcare facilities.
- Improving access to Clinical Breast Examinations in all Health Care Facilities and Imaging techniques for screening breast cancer enables the detection of breast cancer at an earlier stage.

Statement of Ethics: No. IEC-CMC/Approval/19/2023, Institutional Ethics Committee, Chengalpattu Medical College, Chengalpattu.

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